

Article:

The Hybrid Virtual / Traditional Office Work Environment:
Business Processes and Task Uncertainty

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Abstract

Joan Woodward, a principal contributor to the development of the Contingency Theory, argued that an organization's methods are determined by the class of 'core technologies' that characterize its work. Woodward's approach was unique in that she included process in the dichotomy of nonroutine and routine for identifying changes to processes; and the effects, if any, on controlling and productivity. American sociologist James D. Thompson's perspective is that dealing with uncertainty is a fundamental problem best dealt with by the boundary spanning units; thereby, allowing organizations to protect their core technologies. The purpose of this article is to review and apply existing research by Joan Woodward and James D. Thompson to the current hybrid virtual / traditional office work environment. The objective is to identify task uncertainty, if any, created by changes to nonroutine and routine business processes in the hybrid virtual / traditional work environment. Then, the challenge is to determine if revisions are required at the organizational level; e.g. organizational design and structure. The objective is significant in that the hybrid virtual / traditional office work environment has been increasing steadily; with a marked increase, due to the pandemic during the latter part of 2019 and the year 2020.

Keywords: hybrid virtual / traditional work environment; nonroutine and routine work; core technologies; controlling; productivity; boundary spanning units; task uncertainty.

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Introduction

Joan Woodward, a principal contributor to the development of the Contingency Theory, argued that an organization's methods are determined by the class of 'core technologies' that characterize its work. She identified the core technologies as small batch, where the work must be adapted to the peculiarities of the current batch—e.g., emergency medical care and residential construction; large batch, such as automobile manufacturing; or continuous processing, as in petroleum refining (Britannica, n.d.). Woodward's approach was unique in that she digressed from the general discussion of routine and nonroutine of the unit-mass production to include processes (Barbini & Masino, Eds., 2017, p. 15). Then, "working within Woodward's definitional framework, American sociologist James D. Thompson showed that, because the characteristic forms of task uncertainty vary by type, so also does optimal organizational design" (Britannica, n.d.). Fundamentally, both Woodward (1965) and Thompson (1967), recognized that organizational structure is determined by the situational factor of the internal technology of the organization (Barbini & Masino, Eds., 2017, p. 9).

Currently, the hybrid (virtual / traditional office) work environment redesigns business processes, routine and nonroutine, that are the substance of what the company does. That is, the standardization of work is no longer the norm. Instead, there is a lack of specificity of task methods and predictability of (interim) task results. Hence, the foundation of the organizational design, the processes between and within business units and inter-related functions, are subject to formal or, sometimes, informal revisions (Zeller, 2017). Furthermore, as tasks increase in uncertainty, the organizational structure with hierarchical forms of control are frequently replaced with horizontal structures (Zeller, 2017).

The purpose of this article is to review existing research by theorists Joan Woodward and James D. Thompson; then apply their research to the current hybrid virtual / traditional office environment. The objective is to identify task uncertainty, if any, created by changes to routine and nonroutine business processes in the hybrid virtual / traditional work environment. Then, the challenge is to determine if revisions are required at the organizational level; e.g. organizational design and structure (Lin, 2011)(Zeller, 2017). The transnational model of multinational organizations, selected for this article, are global enterprises; hence, the information will include an international perspective.

Definitions

For this study, the hybrid work environment will refer to transnational organizations with virtual offsite and traditional 'brick and mortar' offices.

The following is a list of general terms, as applied to the topic of this paper.

Organizations: "A social unit of people that is structured and managed to meet a need or to pursue collective goals. All organizations have a management structure that determines relationships between the different activities and the members and subdivides and assigns roles, responsibilities, and

authority to carry out different tasks. Organizations are open systems — they affect and are affected by their environment” (BusinessDictionary.com, n.d.).

Organizational Design: “A formal process of integrating people, information and technology together in the right mix to achieve objectives” (Study.com, n.d.). The design is fundamental to determining “the manner in which a management achieves the right combination of differentiation and integration of the organization’s operations, in response to the level of uncertainty in its external environment” (Business Dictionary.com, n.d.).

Organizational Structure: The definition of the term organizational structure includes task allocation, the coordination of processes between internal and external units and members, and the role of decision-makers (Gutterman, 2013).

Task Uncertainty: “The degree to which tasks are open to chance-based, task-relevant influences. It refers to a lack of specificity of task methods and predictability of (interim) task results. With lower levels of task uncertainty, employees know in great detail which task methods to use and which results may be expected. In other words, they have complete knowledge about cause and effect relationships within the task. On the other hand, with higher levels of task uncertainty, task methods leading to task results can only be very generally described and employees do not exactly know which results may be expected; their task knowledge with regard to cause and effect relationships is limited” (Geer-Rutten-Rijswijk, van der, E., 2008).

Purpose and Significance

The overall purpose of this article is to review existing research by theorists Joan Woodward (1965) and James D. Thompson (1967); then apply their research to the current hybrid virtual / traditional office environment. The objective is to identify task uncertainty, if any, created by changes to routine and nonroutine business processes in the hybrid virtual / traditional work environment. The challenge is to determine if, as a result of the uncertainty, revisions are required at the organizational level; e.g. organizational design and structure (Lin, 2011)(Zeller, 2017). The transnational model of multinational organizations, selected for this article, are global enterprises; hence, the information will include an international perspective.

The objective is significant in that the hybrid virtual / traditional office work environment has been increasing steadily; with a marked increase, due to the pandemic during the latter part of 2019 and the year 2020. Nicholas Bloom, the William D. Eberle Professor of Economics in Stanford’s School of Humanities and Science and a senior fellow at the Stanford Institute for Economic Policy Research (SIEPR), noted that currently “an incredible 42 percent of the U.S. labor force are now working full-time from home. By sheer numbers, the United States is a working-from-home economy. Almost twice as many employees are working from home as at work” (Wong, 2020). Some companies, like Twitter and Salesforce, have already announced that they have long-term plans to maintain the work-from-home

option. In addition, 70% of CEOs of large companies have realized the savings on overhead costs and have announced plans to downsize their office space (Westfall, 2020).

Discussion

Whereas organizational design is the manner in which management achieves the right combination of differentiation and integration of the organization's operations, in response to the level of uncertainty in the environment; organizational structure is defined as the framework of the relations of jobs, systems, operating processes, people and groups making efforts to achieve the goals (BusinessDictionary.com, n.d.)(Zeller, 2018). Within that framework, standardization of work processes occurs "when the contents of the work are specified, or programmed" (Mintzberg, 1979, p. 5). In contrast, task uncertainty is the degree to which tasks are open to chance-based, task-relevant influences. It refers to a lack of specificity of task methods and predictability of (interim) task results.

Essentially, the hybrid (virtual / traditional office) work environment redesigns business processes that are the substance of what the company does. The challenge is to identify task uncertainty, if any, resulting from changes to routine and nonroutine business processes introduced in the hybrid virtual / traditional work environment; then determine if revisions are required at the organizational level; e.g. organizational design and structure.

Joan Woodward

The hybrid virtual / traditional office environment will be viewed through the lense of Woodward's tri-part inclusion of process in the dichotomy of nonroutine and routine for identifying changes thereof; and the effects, if any, on controlling and productivity (Barbini & Masino, Eds., 2017, p. 15). The issue is to identify the extent to which production is affected by revised nonroutine and routine work processes in the hybrid (virtual / traditional) work environment (Piernot & Mileti, 1976, p. 2).

In the transition to a hybrid virtual / traditional work environment, the routine and nonroutine processes that are linked to coordinate task interdependence between units and subunits, is subject to change (Zeller, 2017). Rather than revoke their virtual work policy, Microsoft elected to identify changes to workflow, procedures, structures and systems; realign them to fit current business realities/goals; and then to develop plans to implement the new processes. That is, Microsoft was able to link revised routine and nonroutine processes to coordinate task interdependence between units and subunits of people, information, and technology in the hybrid (virtual / traditional) work environment (Zeller, 2018).

Woodward (1965, 1980) also recognized that with advances in technology, "the entire concept of authority in industry may have to change" (p. 30). Research indicates that "organizations with more routine primary task operations will evidence higher levels of formalization than those organizations with

more non-routine primary task operations” (Perinot & Mileti, 1976, p. 20). In a non-routine primary task context, such as in virtual offices, “workers will have more autonomy and responsibility than in traditional offices; however, lines of authority, roles, and responsibilities will still need to be defined clearly” (Cascio, 2000, p. 89). For example, Intuit recognizes that work is a partnership that requires setting expectations for their hybrid traditional and virtual workforce. In order to sustain that partnership, Intuit's hiring managers are able to define role expectations, locations, and then continue to work with employees to make sure that expectations are aligned. Additionally, Intuit’s management includes an Engagement Specialist, dedicated to the virtual workforce, to coordinate offerings that are global and virtual (Fell, 2015)(Zeller, 2017).

“Woodward’s analysis of technology by a ‘scale of technical complexity’, or ‘the extent to which the production process is controllable and its results predictable’”, are evolving in the hybrid (virtual / traditional) work environment (Piernot & Mileti, 1976, p. 2). Perhaps more so for managers used to observing work in process, tracking productivity electronically can be a challenge (Zeller, 2018).

For instance, controlling requires establishing performance standards based on organizational objectives, measuring and reporting on actual performance, comparing results with performance and standards, and taking corrective and preventive measures as needed. In 2004, researchers, Piccoli, Powell, and Ives recognized the potential problems that may accompany the blind transfer of practices used in the traditional environment to the virtual environment. Hence, they encouraged creating and testing management control schemes particularly for the virtual workplace that explicitly account for the characteristics and challenges of the virtual environment (Zeller, 2019).

Nevertheless, predicting the productivity of the virtual workforce continues to be an evolving science; and a combined virtual and traditional workforce presents additional challenges (Zeller, 2018). The crux of the issue is that “in executing an uncertain task, as in any task, employees need to have knowledge about the most appropriate methods to attain optimal results” (Geer-Rutten-Rijswijk, 2008, p. 5). From a production process standpoint, knowledge sharing can be used to streamline standardized business processes as well as remove those that are obsolete (Bhojaraju, 2005). On the other hand, physical location or spatial proximity of the hybrid work environment may change the flow of information on “interrelated business practices”; thereby, affecting the prediction on the results of productivity (Zeller, 2017). In the transnational model, the physical location is further complicated as operations are guided by local context as well as by “close cooperation and interdependence among its headquarters, operations, and international subsidiaries” (Zwass, 1998).

James D. Thompson

James D. Thompson’s perspective is that uncertainty is a fundamental problem and coping with uncertainty is the essence of the administrative process. By allowing the boundary spanning units to deal with uncertainties, the organization protects its core technologies (Mintzberg, 1979, p.21). The issue is

whether the transition to the hybrid virtual / traditional office work environment has created uncertainties that are beyond the administrative processes of the boundary spanning units.

“To Thompson, uncertainty appears as the fundamental problem for complex organizations, and coping with uncertainty, as the essence of the administrative process” (Mintzberg, 1979, p. 21). From Thompson’s viewpoint, organizations protect their core technologies by allowing the boundary spanning units; e.g. research, marketing, and information technology, to deal with uncertainties (Mintzberg, 1979, p.21-22). The boundary spanning units are further supported as business organizations are prone to define structure by those activities (Zeller, 2017). Nevertheless, organizations may overlook limitations thereof as there is a tendency to take for granted the institutional processes to which they adhere (Zeller, 2017).

However, as is being seen in the hybrid (virtual / traditional) environments, the actual system of roles underlying the organizational processes can deviate from the scheduled processes that are the foundation for the formal organizational structure (Cordes-Berszinn, 2013).(Zeller, 2018, Spring). As their working models often displace boundaries and redefine their meanings, boundary analysis is useful for understanding the design of hybrid (virtual / traditional) office work environments. Nevertheless, the taking for granted of the process delegated to the boundary spanning units may or may not be fully protecting core technologies. Hence, in their studies, Lawrence and Suddaby (2012) urge researchers to look behind the scenes of the outward appearance of permanent processes in the organization; and to focus on the gap between action (business processes) and organizational structure (Zeller, 2018, Spring). That is, an ongoing examination of the relationships between organization level changes, described in terms of virtualization activities; and changes to the organization’s working arrangements, described in terms of work units’ boundary properties and activities, is needed to discover gaps (Zeller, 2018, Spring).

“Thompson pointed to the interdependence between stages in the production process as a ‘determining’ factor” (Barbini & Masino, Eds., 2017, p. 9). “Following Woodward and Perrow’s emphasis on variability in the routineness of work, Thompson recognized that work processes associated with a technology vary in the extent to which they are interrelated. He called this ‘variable task’ to emphasize the issue of dependence on others for the accomplishment of tasks” (Barbini & Masino, Eds., 2017, p. 15-16). For example, in an insurance firm transitioning to a hybrid workplace, the increase in the number of applications processed from the virtual office produced a bottle-neck of work for the next part of processing in a traditional ‘brick and mortar’ office based department; thereby, affecting the agents, who were dependent on those others for the accomplishment of their task; e.g. their approval of the policy. Subsequently, the reason for the bottle-neck was discovered and changes were made to the design of the business processes, as well as the structure; e.g. report-to managers and supervisors (Zeller 2017).

“Work-flow interdependencies are not the only ones to be taken into consideration by the designer of organizational structure; a second class of interdependencies relates to the processes used within the workflow” (Mintzberg, 1979, p. 122). Essentially, marketing at IBM was no longer a ‘waterfall’ process where work was handed from one person to the next. Instead, due to global market

changes, the Marketing Department required working shoulder-to-shoulder to promote real-time decisions. Hence, 2,600 virtual workers were required to work or 'co-locate' to one of six cities; e.g. adapting the design of the processes within the workflow and the structure (Weller, 2017)(Zeller, 2018, Summer).

Overall, "during high times of uncertainty for organizations, greater organizational effectiveness is achieved through high differentiation, the segmentation of the organizational system into subsystems; coupled with high integration, the process of achieving unity of effort" (Business Dictionary.com, n.d.). As noted in the case studies, in response to the level of uncertainty in the external market, the transitioning insurance company and IBM revised organizational designs and structures. The changes were based on the interdependence of the workflow (redesign of segmentation of the subsystems in the transitioning insurance company), and the processes within the workflow (integration in the marketing department at IBM) (Zeller, 2017, Sept).

Summary and Recommendations for Future Research

Woodward's tri-part inclusion of process in the dichotomy of nonroutine and routine was applied for identifying changes to processes; and the effects, if any, on controlling and productivity. Predicting the productivity of the virtual workforce continues to be an evolving science; and a combined virtual and traditional workforce presents additional challenges. Generally, organizations in which virtual-work arrangements thrive will be flatter than the traditional hierarchy, Furthermore, workers within these environments will have more autonomy and responsibility; thereby, influencing nonroutine and routine processes. Moreover, Woodward proposed that with advances in technology, the entire concept of authority in industry may have to change. Woodward also emphasized how changes in markets led to product innovation which then led to changes in technology and subsequently organizational structures. Essentially, lines of authority, roles, and responsibilities will need to be defined clearly; possibly requiring changes to design and structure.

Thompson identified task uncertainty as a fundamental problem for complex organizations, and coping with uncertainty, as the essence of the administrative process. From Thompson's viewpoint, organizations protect their core technologies by allowing the boundary spanning units; e.g. marketing, finance, and information technology, to deal with uncertainties. Furthermore, Thompson recognized that work processes associated with a technology vary in the extent to which they are interrelated. He called this 'variable task' to emphasize the issue of dependence on others for the accomplishment of tasks. In addition, there are interdependencies of the processes within the workflow. In either case, during high times of uncertainty for organizations, the recommendation is to look behind the scenes of the outward appearance of permanent processes in the organization; e.g. the boundary spanning units.

Future research recommendations include applying organizational theories; e.g. classical, neoclassical, modern; to the current day hybrid virtual / traditional office work environment. For example, the foundation of the Modern Systems Theory is the principle that all of an organization's

components interrelate nonlinearly; therefore, making a small change in one variable impacts many others (Zeller, 2018, Summer). Do the changes to business processes, if any, contribute to task uncertainty; thereby, affecting other areas? Are the boundary spanning units proactively identifying those areas? In addition, the work of researchers Hage and Aiken “found that organizations with more routine work are more centralized in decision making and more formalized by the presence of rules, manuals and specificity of job descriptions” (Piernot & Mileti, 1976, p.19). Does the hybrid virtual / traditional work environment change standardized routine work; thereby, changing decision making, formalized rules, and job specificity?

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